

1 Supporting Figures

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5 **Figure S1.** Phylogeny of identified bacteria from *Laodelphax striatellus* using a ML tree (A) and
6 a Bio-NJ tree based on 16S rRNA gene sequences. The bootstrap values (>50) are shown at the
7 nodes. Scale bar means the expected number of substitutions per site. The host species name and
8 NCBI accession numbers are shown. The sequences obtained in this study are shown in Table S2.

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10 **Figure S2.** Phylogeny of *Asaia* using a ML tree (A) and a Bio-NJ tree based on 16S rRNA gene
 11 sequences. The bootstrap values (>50) are shown at the nodes. Scale bar means the expected
 12 number of substitutions per site. The bacterial species name and NCBI accession numbers are
 13 shown. The sequences obtained in this study are shown in Table S2.

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16 Table S1 RFLP patterns of the 16S rRNA genes amplicons

17 Table S2 Amplified bacterial 16S rRNA gene sequences from *L. striatellus*

18 Table S3 NCBI blast hits of the 16S rRNA gene sequences obtained in this study

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